

EFFECT OF FREQUENCY ON DELAMINATION CRACK GROWTH IN HIGH TEMPERATURE FATIGUE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CF/PEEK COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The behavior of Mode I delamination crack propagation of a unidirectional CF/PEEK composite was investigated in fatigue at 473K (200°C). The crack propagation was classified into two types: cycle-dependent and time-dependent ones. In the former, the crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , was correlated well with the range of energy release rate, ΔG . In the latter, the propagation rate per unit time, dl/dt , is governed by the energy release rate, G , and the dl/dt - G relation coincided with that in static creep. The transient condition between them was derived by equating the crack extension in a cycle due to creep (dl/dt - G) and fatigue (dl/dN - ΔG).

1. INTRODUCTION

As structural components of advanced aerospace plane are anticipated to be exposed in high temperature environment, it is required for the materials not only to have superior relative strength but also to hold the durability at high temperatures. Although the conventional carbon fiber reinforced polymers such as CF/Epoxy which are employed as primary structure of airplanes have presented excellent performance in the relative strength, the application to the high temperature use is questionable. The effort has been made on the development of advanced CFRP which is durable up to 473K(200°C)~573K(300°C) using high-performance polymers as the matrix. In order to ensure the reliability of advanced component, it is inevitable to understand the mechanism and the mechanics of failure at high temperature. Few works, however, have been done on them though the creep influences the strength of polymer [1,2].

In this paper, the behavior of delamination crack propagation of CF/PEEK composite is experimentally investigated in high temperature fatigue on the basis of fracture mechanics concept.

Table I Test material and mechanical properties at room temperature.

Prepreg Carbon fiber Matrix	APC-2 AS4 PEEK
Volume fraction of fiber	62%
Constitution of laminate	(0)48
Crystallinity of PEEK	34%
Elastic constants at room temperature (GPa)	$E_1=134, E_2=8.9, G_{12}=5.1,$ $\nu_{12}=0.31$

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material and Specimen

Unidirectional laminate of 6mm in thickness is made from 48plies of the APC-2 prepregs which consist of the carbon fibers, AS4, and the thermoplastic polymer, poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK). Table I summarizes the constitution of laminate and the elastic constants at room temperatureeristics of matrix.

All tests were carried out using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens where the fibers are aligned to the direction of crack propagation. The dimension and the configuration of specimen are illustrated in Fig. 1. A starter slit of 40~50mm in length was introduced into the specimen by inserting aluminum film (15 μm in thickness) during the fabrication. The load was applied to the specimen through hinges fixed at the specimen edges (Fig. 1).

The following relationship between the elastic compliance, λ , and the crack length, l , is proposed for the DCB specimen [3].

$$\lambda^{1/3} = C_0 + C_1(l/h) \quad (1)$$

where C_0 and C_1 are constants and h is the half thickness of specimen. The elastic compliance of the DCB specimen used in this study is experimentally examined at 473K (200°C) by measuring the cross head displacement as the crack opening displacement. Using the least square method for data fitting, the values of constants, C_0 and C_1 , are determined as 0.466 and 0.0450, respectively (λ in $\text{N}/\mu\text{m}$ and l in μm). The elastic energy release rate, G , is evaluated by

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2B} \times \frac{d\lambda}{dl} \quad (2)$$

where P is the load and B is the width of specimen.

Fig.1 Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen (dimensions are in mm).

2.2 Test Conditions

Load-controlled tests were conducted in creep and fatigue conditions at 473K (200 °C). The temperature was monitored by a few sets of thermocouples attached to the specimen and was controlled within $\pm 3K$ during the tests. The fatigue tests were carried out by an electric-mechanical testing machine or an electric-hydraulic one with a radiation furnace. The specimens were subjected to trapezoidal or sinusoidal load waveforms with the load ratio, $R(=P_{min}/P_{max})$, of 0.1. The period of cycle, $1/\nu$, was chosen in the extent of 0.5s to 4992s in order to examine the creep effect on the crack propagation. The creep tests were carried out under sustained load of 228N and 249N by a creep testing machine where dead weight was applied directly at the foot of lower pull-rod [1,2]. The testing conditions are summarized in Table II. The crack length was measured by means of an optical microscope with the magnification of 50 times through the window on the furnace.

Table II Test conditions.

Load waveform				Static creep							
R=Pmin/Pmax	0.1			-							
Pmax(N)	150	228	190	228	249						
1/ν (s)	0.5	0.5	0.5	2	20	1752	4992	4764	-	-	
tH(s)	-	-	-	1	10	360	3600	3600	-	-	
Symbol in figures	▽	○	△	□	◇	●	●	▲	■	×	+

Fig. 2 Relationship between crack propagation rate per unit time, dl/dt , and period of load cycle, $1/\nu$, under $G_{max}=1567N/m$.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the dependence of crack propagation rate per unit time, dl/dt , on the period of load cycle, $1/\nu$, for an equal value of energy release rate at the maximum load. It reveals that the relationship is distinctly classified into two regions. The crack propagation rate, dl/dt , is independent of the period of cycle in $1/\nu \geq 20s$, while it is inversely proportional to the period in $1/\nu < 20s$. In the latter, the crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , is independent of the period. This implies that the propagation is purely time-dependent in the former while it is purely cycle-dependent in the latter. It has been reported for metallic materials that intermediate behavior, which is called "creep-fatigue interaction", is usually observed between them[4,5]. Figure 2 discloses no interaction in the crack propagation of the CF/PEEK in high-temperature fatigue.

3.1 Time-Dependent Crack Propagation

The delamination of the CF/PEEK under static creep at 443K (170 °C) ~ 473K (210 °C) was investigated in previous papers [1,2] in detail. The crack propagation attributed to the matrix creep which caused the failure along the boundary between fibers and matrix. The creep deformation in the matrix was confined near the crack tip due to the constraint by the fibers and the elastic deformation dominated the specimen. The crack propagated under small scale creep (SSC) condition as schematically illustrated in Fig.3. Therefore, the propagation rate, dl/dt , was correlated well with the elastic energy release rate, G . In a monolithic material, the creep zone swiftly expands and reaches to large scale creep (LSC) condition where the creep deformation dominates the whole specimen. G is not applicable to the propagation in the LSC condition because of nonlinear deformation [6]. Consequently, the creep crack propagation of CFRP is characterized by the SSC condition due to the constraint of fibers where the elastic fracture mechanics parameter governs the stress intensity in the vicinity of the crack tip.

Fig.3 Schematic illustration explaining small scale creep (SSC).

The propagation rate, dl/dt , in the creep-fatigue of $1/\nu > 20s$ is plotted against the elastic energy release rate, G , at the sustained load in Fig.4(a). The propagation rate is correlated well with G and the relationship coincides with the marks, + and ×, which indicate the results in static creep. This implies that the matrix creep brought about the time-dependence on the crack propagation in cyclic loading, and the fibers prevented the expansion of creep zone. The relation between dl/dt (mm/h) and G (N/m) is formulated as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} dl/dt &= C_c G^{5c} \\ &= 5.85 \times 10^{-34} G^{10.2} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where C_c and m_c are the material constants. It is worthy of note that the stress change does not influence the creep crack propagation. In other words, the time-dependent crack propagation due to creep is estimated by Eq.(3) not only in the trapezoidal load waveform but also general fatigue conditions.

Figure 4(b) shows the relationship between dl/dt and G in $1/\nu \leq 20s$. In the fatigue under the sinusoidal load waveform, dl/dt , which is calculated from $\nu \cdot dl/dN$, is plotted against the energy release rate at the maximum load. The hatched band in the figure indicates the relationship in the time-dependent crack propagation. Although the relationship in $\nu = 20s$ is within the band, the others present eminent acceleration for an equal magnitude of G . It suggests that different mechanics governs the crack propagation in the fatigue of $1/\nu < 20s$ while Eq.(3) is applicable to the boundary ($1/\nu = 20s$) between the time-dependent propagation and the cycle-dependent one.

Fig.4 Relationship between crack propagation rate per unit time, dl/dt , and energy release rate, G .

3.2 Cycle-Dependent Crack Propagation

Figure 5(a) shows the relationship between the crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , and the range of energy release rate, ΔG , in the purely cycle-dependent fatigue of $1/\nu < 20s$. ΔG is defined as

$$\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min} \tag{4}$$

where G_{max} and G_{min} are the energy release rate at the maximum and the minimum load in a cycle, respectively. dl/dt is governed by ΔG , which implies the propagation in the small scale yielding condition. Moreover, it suggests that the propagation mechanism is similar to that in room temperature fatigue. The relationship between dl/dN (mm/cycle) and ΔG (N/m) is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 dl/dN &= C^f \Delta G^{5.3} \\
 &= 2.29 \times 10^{-20} \Delta G^{5.3}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

The dotted line in the figure indicates the relationship of the CF/PEEK between dl/dN and ΔG in room temperature fatigue with the stress ratio of 0.2 and the loading frequency of 10 Hz [7]. The crack propagation rate at 473K is slower than that at room temperature. The improvement in the resistance to the crack propagation may attribute to the higher ductility of the thermoplastic polymer at 473K.

The crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , in $1/\nu \geq 20s$ is plotted against the range of energy release rate, ΔG , in Fig.5(b). The hatched band indicates the relationship in the cycle-dependent crack propagation. The figure exhibits the eminent acceleration of the propagation for an equal magnitude of ΔG while Eq. (5) as well as Eq. (3) is applicable to the boundary ($1/\nu = 20s$).

Fig.5 Relationship between crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , and range of energy release rate, ΔG .

3.3 Transient Condition Between Cycle-Dependent Crack Propagation and Time-Dependent One

Since little interaction was observed between the time-dependent (creep) crack propagation and the cycle-dependent (fatigue) one, the transient condition is given by comparing the contribution due to creep and fatigue. The condition is formulated as

$$(dl/dN)_{creep} = (dl/dN)_{fatigue}
 \tag{6}$$

where $(dl/dN)_{creep}$ and $(dl/dN)_{fatigue}$ are crack propagation in a cycle due to creep and fatigue, respectively. While $(dl/dN)_{fatigue}$ is obtained from Eq. (5), $(dl/dt)_{creep}$ is calculated by the integral of Eq. (3) during the tensile half cycle, t_1 ,

$$(dl/dN)_{creep} = \int_0^{t_i} C_c G^{5.3} dt \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3) and (6) into Eq. (7),

$$\int_0^{t_i} G^{5.3} dt = (C_f/C_c) \Delta G^{5.3} \quad (8)$$

Then, the transient condition for the CF/PEEK is given by

$$\int_0^{t_i} G^{10.2} dt = 3.91 \times 10^{13} \Delta G^{5.3} \quad (9)$$

Figure 6 shows the relationship between $\int_0^{t_i} G^{10.2} dt$ and $\Delta G^{5.3}$ where the solid line indicates the transient condition. It proves the validity of Eq. (8) as the transient condition.

Fig.6 Transient condition between cycle-dependent crack propagation and cycle-dependent one.

4. Conclusion

The delamination crack propagation was investigated in high temperature fatigue using the DCB specimen of a unidirectional CF/PEEK composite. The results obtained are summarized as follows.

- (1) The behavior of crack propagation in high temperature fatigue was classified into two types: the cycle-dependent type and the time-dependent one.
- (2) In the cycle-dependent type, the crack propagation rate per unit cycle, dl/dN , was correlated well with the range of energy release rate, ΔG .

(3) In the time-dependent type, the propagation rate per unit time, dl/dt , was correlated well with the energy release rate, G , and the relation coincided with that in static creep. This implied that the time-dependent crack propagation was characterized by the small scale creep condition where the creep deformation in the matrix was confined near the crack tip due to the constraint of fibers.

(4) The transient condition between the two types was given by Eq.(8) as a function of ΔG and G equating the crack extension due to creep and fatigue during a cycle.

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References

1. Ohtani, R., Kitamura, T., Morita, H., Yamada, M. and Hojo, M., Trans. JSME, Ser. A, Vol. 57, No. 535, 1991, pp. 556-562 (in Japanese).
2. Ohtani, R., Kitamura, T., Uematsu, Y. and Hojo, M., ASTM STP 1174, American Society for Testing Materials, Philadelphia, USA, 1993, pp. 23-38.
3. Kageyama, K., Kobayashi, T. and Nonaka, K., Trans. JSME, Ser. A, Vol. 53, No. 494, 1987, pp. 1898-1904 (in Japanese).
4. Solomon, H.D. and Coffin, L.F.Jr., ASTM STP 520, American Society for Testing Materials, Philadelphia, USA, 1973, pp. 112-122.
5. Ohtani, R., Kitamura, T. and Yamada, K., Fracture Mechanics of Ductile and Tough Materials and Its Applications to Energy Related Structures, Proc. USA-JAPAN Joint Seminar 1979, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1981, pp. 263-270.
6. Kuwabara, K., Nitta, A., Kitamura, T. and Ogata, T., ASTM STP 924, American Society for Testing Materials, Philadelphia, USA, 1988, pp. 41-59.
7. Hojo, M., Tanaka, K., Gustafson, C.-G., Gradin, P.A. and Kenmochi, K., Trans. JSME, Ser. A, Vol. 56, No. 526, 1990, pp. 1327-1334 (in Japanese).